

DEVELOPING THE TEACHER'S CREATIVE TOUCH IN THE ORGANIZATION OF KAZAKH LANGUAGE CLASSES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. *The role of the primary school teacher in the organization of the mother tongue lesson. Creative tasks used in the mother tongue lesson and their application.*

Keywords: *creative, creative, cognitive activity, didactic task.*

Introduction

The teacher is the pillar, the heart, and the handle of knowledge of the school. Everyone knows that the main person in whose hands the fate of the child is entrusted is the teacher. K.D. Ushinsky's opinion was expressed by P.F. Kapterev further developed the pedagogical process as a joint action of the student and the teacher: on the one hand, it is the guidance of the teacher, and on the other hand, the internal action of the student. He paid special attention to the student's active learning, interest, and effort. Kapterev prioritized the study of the student's internal processes in acquiring knowledge. The most important thing is to create favorable conditions for these processes. Y. Altynsarin made a great contribution to solving didactic tasks in Kazakh schools. Altynsarin's requirements about teacher duties, how to teach, how to study are of great importance today. According to Y. Altynsarin, individual methods of teaching include: arousing the child's desire for knowledge; guide to self-education; train the child's thinking in class.

If we say that education, science, and education are the core of an educated generation, the end of civilization, the beginning of all this is primary school. And the main task of the primary generation is to ensure the initial formation of the child's personality, to develop his abilities, to instill in the student the noble qualities of humanity. Some studies explain the student's cognitive activity as a continuous learning process aimed at intellectual and professional training, optimizing the level of learning efficiency and scientific learning.

Education of the child's creative activities, national culture and spiritual values is carried out through the mother tongue. About the importance of this subject, Zh. Aimautov says: "There is no doubt that mother tongue is the subject that is equally necessary for all taught subjects, and the subject that wraps everything up and wraps everything up. It is impossible to understand other subjects without mastering the mother tongue. Learning one's mother tongue is not only memorizing words, knowing their system, the laws of change, but in addition to learning the language, the child also learns countless concepts, thoughts, feelings, beautiful models, the thinking system, philosophy of the language. And the formation of creative activity through teaching the native language means striving for self-awareness in the reality of life, searching. In this regard, V.V. Davydov says: "Creative abilities are manifested in the activity of learning in primary school, the product of development is a desire to learn, enthusiasm." And creativity can be in the nature of every child. Our task is to reveal the hidden possibilities to the student. The only thing a teacher needs to fulfill these tasks is to select and use the correct and effective methods. I have achieved some results using new technologies in my practice. If this work is

properly organized, the student's thinking will be strengthened according to his level of development and he will definitely achieve certain achievements. The teacher leads the student to search for himself, teaches him to think, directs him to various activities. Types of tenses aimed at forming students' cognitive inquisitiveness are divided into four: cognitive, communicative, creative, methodological.

It is very important to conduct classes of a creative nature in increasing the cognitive inquisitiveness of students. Various educational activities in such classes increase the student's real activity, learn effective methods of reading and thinking, that is, distinguishing the main concepts and conclusions of the material, comparing new material with past material, grouping them into a known system, and learning to prepare methods such as making summaries.

Research materials and methodology

The concept of "creative" means the level of creativity, talent, flexibility to creativity. The structure of a person's creative competence includes the following qualities: flexibility to creativity, problem solving, self-confidence, flexibility to analysis. It is better for every teacher to feel the existence of the owner of a profession with unlimited responsibility and great value in providing education and upbringing to the next generation. After all, the main mechanism for raising the quality of education in training a competitive person is an educated and creative teacher.

When making a plan of creative lessons, it should be adapted to the orientation of the creative activity of the student, and their abilities should be taken into account. If we say that the most important condition for the development of society is the education of a creative person, the ability to educate that creative person only by a creative teacher requires the knowledge and professional skills of teachers and learners. Therefore, being able to use the currently used critical thinking development technology according to the specifics of the subject is the only way to achieve the educational goal. The folk proverb "Let your courage be accompanied by your method, and your mind be accompanied by your method" should become the position of the leader of the nation.

To create a creative lesson plan topic, purpose, type of action and results are close to each other you can group and select related lessons. Based on the achievements in each chapter of the subject lessons specified in the general program, students achieve results in education. It is up to the teacher to raise the creative potential of students aims. The teacher enters the student's state, thinks about their attitude towards the topic, makes corrections to the planned lesson content and teaching methods if necessary, for the problem of the lesson.

The teacher gets acquainted with textbooks, books, methodical books and other materials on the topic of the lesson. The teacher looks for problems that are strong for him and the students. It is necessary to find many materials on these issues, taking into account the opinions of experts.

Creativity is a person's search for self-awareness in the reality of life. In order to find the right path in life, a person needs to learn to think correctly and make quality, reasoned decisions on his own. Developing human abilities and not allowing them to die, strengthens his spiritual strength and helps him find his place in life. Because man is not only a creation but also a creator. Features of the creative lesson: Traditional lesson; Creative lesson.

Search results

Creative tasks used in the mother tongue lesson:

Various methods of engaging students in creative work and increasing their activity, interest, and creative abilities: Text, fairy tale, completing the story independently. Completing ready-made texts of poets and writers in a different way. Write a story based on a well-known

proverb. Compose a sentence based on the text. Compose a puzzle based on natural phenomena, objects and individual pictures. Comparing stories, dividing them into parts. Creation of works, texts, fairy tales. (by topic, by plan, by supporting words). Composition of poems and proverbs. Telling stories similar to the stories in the work. Characterization of the character. Drawing based on the work, verbal description, drawing through imagination, sculpting. Role-based learning. Solving tasks with games that develop logical thinking (anagrams, crosswords, rebus). Dialogue-tale. Enter the image.

Creative tasks: getting into the image, analysis and imagination, poet, dialogue-fairytale, puzzle-proverbs composition. Task 1 "Getting into the image" - to feel what kind of state and function they perform in their places of inanimate objects, plants, animals. I am a flower. Writing stories on different topics (I'm a spoon, I'm a tree, I'm a guide, I'm a ball). Story of 1 student: I am a flower. I grow on earth. I need air, water, heat, light, food. I bring joy to people. People honor me to bring happiness and joy to their mothers and teachers.

People judge me. I am different. I smell good. People love me. I will not harm anyone. Through this, students' thinking is expanded and their language is developed.

Task II "Analysis and Imagination" - analysis of works, examples of fiction has a great impact on the development of thinking, abilities, and creativity of primary school students. An unanalyzed work reaches a child's heart and does not move it. In the story "Care" of the 3rd grade, children will be analyzed and questions will be answered. With this, it is possible to bring the students to a situation where they experience the stages of creative activity such as passion, imagination, flash of ideas, and inspiration.

III task "Pull-out poet" - in primary classes, it is better to start the first stage of creativity in the form of activities and games. By being interested in playing games, the child's thinking field and free imagination and creative thinking are formed. For example, during the "Rain Game", the students demonstrate the phenomena described by the teacher at that moment, each of them independently, through their actions: thunder played, rain dripped, the wind increased, it poured heavily, and the wind subsided. In this way, having refreshed the students and aroused their interest, it is possible to perform the first stage of drawing according to the poem "Rain". For that, we use the following words: rain, field, mountain, city, forest, village.

Task II "Dialogue-fairytale" - Condition: the teacher or the student invents and starts any story-tale. And the rest of the students continue the story that began one sentence at a time. For example, it starts like this: "Once upon a time, there was a rich man's son..." Student 1: "That son got lost while chasing butterflies on the lawn..." Student 2: "While he was walking with his stomach rumbling, he met a goat..." — this is how the fairy tale continues. The last student must finish the story with a quick decision.

Task V. development of students' thinking by creating riddles and proverbs. In connection with these proverbs, creative tasks such as composition, conversation, writing from the mind, along with teaching competent writing and connecting speech, form an effective thinking process. It helps to solve problems such as language development, instills creativity.

The new content of education sets new requirements for the visual tools used in all subjects, as well as for working with them. Creating a story based on the plot picture "The Last Apple". While walking through the garden, Murat saw a single apple left on the tree... What could happen next? Finish it and write it yourself" - to put the problem in front of them and create a conversation for the students on the topic of "The Last Apple".

"The goal of teaching a child is to make him capable of further development without the help of a teacher," said Elbert Hubbard. For this, the teacher should be interested in the teaching process by introducing new methods of learning with the aim of improving our qualifications. Students should not only listen, but be active in learning. In the framework of active learning, he gets a fun education. Teachers demonstrate their skills in terms of introducing the updated and criterion-referenced evaluation system. Teachers try to understand what students know and can do, as well as their interests, what each student likes and wants to do. We can say that only a teacher who has strengthened his creativity can provide a new and creative education".

Discussions.

The importance of using national games in the process of primary education:

Didactic national game plays an important role in educating a child in a comprehensive manner. Among them, the main function: plays a great role in mental education. According to the content of the didactic national game, educational, educational, visual, vocabulary, and action tasks are performed. That is why there are specific methodological ways:

1. When conducting didactic national games, the teacher teaches the children while keeping the goal of the game. For this, first of all, the teacher himself should be willingly involved in a fun and interesting game and be happy.

2. When organizing a didactic national game, the teacher first makes the game interesting for the child and on that basis increases the child's mental activity.

3. The teacher must make strict demands in the implementation of the established rules. This teaches the child to comply with the requirements and not to break the rules.

4. Only if all children are actively involved in the game can the team achieve the goal of the didactic national game.

In the didactic national game, education and training are closely connected together. What does the student learn through the game? - Develops logical thinking skills; Learns to work independently; Enriches vocabulary, develops language; Attention is formed; Vigilance increases; Teaches mutual respect; Not to break the rules of the game, i.e. to be disciplined; Pupils' trust in each other increases, they learn friendship and cooperation; Interest in the lesson increases.

Depending on the ultimate goal of the game, games can be divided into the following typical groups:

- games depicting domestic phenomena ("playing family", "school", "kindergarten");
- games depicting creative work (building houses, stadiums, building ships);
- drawing social events, games depicting traditions (festive demonstrations, welcoming guests, trips).

This division of games is, of course, only conditional, because the game can include the representation of various phenomena of life. Types of games:

There are many types of games. Among them, used in primary classes: game-lesson, game-training, refreshment games, didactic games, word games, logic games, business games or national games and many others. Such games help the student develop comprehensively and fully master knowledge.

Methodological requirements for the game: The goal of the game is to prepare the necessary visuals and materials in advance and place them in the optimal place; Before starting the game, thoroughly explain the procedure to the students; Ensuring the participation of all students in the class in the game; To lead them to be able to make decisions and think during the game; Selection of game types according to the program;

Changing the game according to the age of the child; Moving from a simple game to a difficult game; The results of the game must be announced. Classification of game types: grammatical; psychological; supporting drawings; logical; technical; physical labor.

Grammar games: Give students a great opportunity to fully master grammar and develop their written language. The process of syntactic and morphological analyzes is continuously developing. In addition, he can learn phonetic rules freely. Among them are: 1) letter and syllable noodles; 2) types of dictation; 3) types of training; 4) works, contents; 5) creating a story, text; 6) dictionaries.

Psychological games are often played by asking questions when faced with an unfamiliar topic. It helps students to share their thoughts, to solve important problems, to be able to openly express how they understood the materials. Among them: 1) psychological test, questionnaires; 2) drawing, assemblies; 3) discussions; 4) question - answers; 5) dictionaries (dialogue, monologue).

Basic drawing games - as the name suggests, these games are mostly about drawing, drawing, designing, and memorizing. The game is closely related to the grammar game. Among them: engravings; picture puzzles; word puzzles, anagrams; including pictures.

Logical games expand students' thinking, language and vocabulary. The game encourages thoughtfulness, inquisitiveness, ingenuity, quickness, and responsibility. The game takes place through the frame of mind. Therefore, it is often given through questions and tasks. Among them: 1) riddles; 2) logical question-tasks;

3) instant tasks.

Physical labor games - most of these games are realized as a result of hard work and sweat. It is closely related to the subject of physical education and is carried out by the skill of the teacher. Among them: 1) refreshing moments; 2) breathing exercises; 3) sports games; 4) include national games.

Conclusion

"Bead" game - The purpose of the game: to repeat and distinguish words with thick and thin roots. Terms of the game: Write words with thick and thin roots on hard paper. Divide the class into two groups and distribute the words written on paper. After the set time, each group needs to string beads from one thick and one thin root word. Whichever group's bead lines up first wins. Necessary words: pharmacy, hospital, medicine, food, capital, forest, duty officer, break, student, eraser, pen, diary, spring, winter, fish, etc. b.

"Cities" game - The purpose of the game: to form words from syllables and learn to write correctly. Terms of the game: Divide the class into two groups and write any syllable of the name of the city on the board. The first group to find the correct word wins. Task samples: snow - Karaganda; food - Astana; apple - Almaty; mountain - Kokshetau; rau - Atyrau; city - Shymkent.

"Question - answer" game - The purpose of the game: to learn to answer questions correctly and quickly. Terms of the game: Divide the class into two groups. Distribute cards with answers to questions to each group. After the question is read, students indicate the correct answer. The group with the most correct answers wins. Questions: 1. What is in the bag? 2. How many days are there in a week? 3. Who is in the dining room? 4. How many windows are there in the classroom? 5. How many fingers are there on the hand? 6. What is the weather like in summer? 7. How many hours are there in a day? 8. How many floors does the school have? 9. What turns yellow in autumn? Required words: pen, seven, cook, three, five, hot, twenty-four, three, leaf.

"Who is the last?" game - The purpose of the game: to expand students' vocabulary by expanding and adding words. Terms of the game: Any word is written on the board. The teacher creates other words related to this word. The student who creates the last word is the winner.

"Magic tree" game - The purpose of the game: to teach students to answer questions. Game conditions: An apple tree made of hard paper is hung on the board. One question is written outside the apples. The student who goes to the blackboard takes the apple and answers the question. If the student answers the question correctly, he keeps the apple. The teacher evaluates the work of each student. This game can be found in "School", "Pets", "Kitchen", "Fish", etc. b. can be held on topics. An example of conducting a game on the topic of family: Questions: 1. What is your family like? 2. How many people are there in your family? 3. What does your father do? 4. What does your mother do? 5. How old is your mother? 6. How old is your father? 7. Who is your grandmother? 8. Is your family friendly? 9. How did you help your father?

"Kitchen" game - The purpose of the game is to repeat the words related to the theme of "Kitchen". Terms of the game: A picture of a chef and words related to the topic are posted on the board. The class is divided into two groups. The group that finds the most words related to the topic is the winner. Keywords: Chef----- Fish; Fork----Dumpling; Pilau-----Porridge; Plate-----Cup; Milk----- Kettle Meat----- Spoon

Delicious-----Soup; Sweet-----Es. This game can be played on different topics.

"Find your place" game - The purpose of the game: to be able to ask the right questions to the words. Terms of the game: Who is on the board? what? what is write down the questions. Write the words that answer these questions on hard paper and distribute them to the students. each student goes to the blackboard and stands next to the question for his speech. This game can be played with points.

"Missing letters" game - The purpose of the game: to train students to write well. Repetition of sounds characteristic of the Kazakh language. Terms of the game: The class is divided into two groups. Write 10 words on the board. For example: k... deer; algae... an; song... ran; k... find; k... ktem; ... eat; ... news; o... ushi; month... ar; a...

The group that correctly forms the necessary letters wins.

"Khojanasir basket" game - The purpose of the game: to develop students' logical thinking skills. Increasing interest in the Kazakh language. The condition of the game: a basket is hung on the board. Telling that this basket is Kojanasyr's basket, it is full of gifts and distributing tasks to students. If the student completes the task correctly, he will win a prize from the basket. Before the game, you can spend a refreshing moment: Come, children, come, see Tamasha. We have an interesting game, everyone be careful. Find the solution to the riddle: "That place of your house, He washes his face and hands, He has the same color as a tiger, He has two alert eyes." (cat)

"Auction" game - The purpose of the game: to expand vocabulary. Education to love the subject. Terms of the game: the class is divided into two groups. Hang the word written on paper

on the board and find out how many points each group will give to this word. Open the word to the group with the most points and ask for the correct translation. If the team answers correctly, the given points go to the team's fund. If the answer is not correct, the point goes to the other team. The team with the most points will be the winner.

"Question - answer" game - The purpose of the game: to learn to answer the question correctly. The condition of the game: make 40 cards from hard paper. Write questions on 20 cards and answers on the remaining 20 cards. Students form a circle. One student walks around with a card with a question on it. The next student clicks with the card that answers the question.

"Find the continuation" game - The purpose of the game is to teach the correct construction of sentences. Condition of the game: divide students into two groups. Write sentences separately on hard paper. Distribute cards to students. Students go to the blackboard and read the beginning of the proverb. The student with the continuation of the proverb goes to him and reads the continuation.

"Magic basket" game - The purpose of the game: to teach students to answer questions. The condition of the game: hang a picture of a basket on the board. Put questions in the basket. Students go out one by one and read the questions from the basket. Questions: Where do you live? What country is your homeland? What is depicted in the coat of arms? What street do you live on? How old are u? What does your father do? Who bakes bread? Who makes boots?

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